

Influence of Pesticides on the Trace Element Status of Soils (BHC on Manganese and Iron)

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The effects of different doses of hexachlorocyclohexane (BHC), a well known insecticide, on the Mn and Fe status of a saline sodic soil were examined. The results revealed that 0.25 g of BHC per kg of soil after an interval of 30 days produced optimum effect on trace element status. At this dose and time interval water soluble Mn, exchangeable Mn, active Mn, exchangeable and available Fe significantly increased while reducible Mn decreased. The effect of the chemical started declining after a period of 4 weeks of application. The responses have been explained on the basis of chemical and microbial activity in soil.

PESTICIDES are widely used in agricultural production. They are used as insecticides, herbicides, fungicides and nematocides. The importance of pesticides in crop production is due to their accumulation in soils and their effect on soil properties. Several workers¹⁻⁶ have studied this subject in considerable detail, but information on the influence of pesticides on the trace element status is lacking.

Mn²⁺ exists in soil as a water soluble and as exchangeable ion and hence in this state is available to plants. Mn⁴⁺ exists as unavailable form but is reducible to available form. Manganese along with iron assists in formation of chlorophyll and control many complicated systems of oxidation-reduction in plants and soils. Iron exists as Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ and its availability is governed by oxidation-reduction potential of the soil. Micro-organisms are mainly responsible for iron transformation.

Hexachlorocyclohexane (BHC) is widely used as an insecticide to control insect pests. In view of the great importance of the trace elements in plants metabolism and the increasing use of pesticides for high crop yields, it was considered that an examination of the effects of BHC on manganese and iron transformation in a saline sodic soil would be useful.

Experimental

The soil used in the study (depth 0-30 cm) was collected from a representative area of Aligarh district. It was dried, crushed and sieved. The general physicochemical characteristics of the soil were determined and yielded the following data: pH = 8.80, electrical conductivity = 4.5×10^{-4} mhos cm⁻¹, organic matter = 0.41%, water soluble Mn = 3.2 ppm, exchangeable Mn = 8.8 ppm, reducible Mn = 61.4 ppm, exchangeable Fe = 11.9 ppm and available Fe = 38.5 ppm.

The experiments on the influence of pesticide on the trace elements were done in earthenware pots of 20 × 20 cm size. They were cleaned and fitted with polythene sheets on the wall of pots towards the inner side to prevent absorption of water. One kg of the soil was then placed in each of the twenty one pots. Seven doses of BHC (0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 g) were then added and mixed with 1 kg of soil in three replications without growing any crop. All the samples were then watered upto the water holding capacity with distilled water every week throughout the period of experiment. The treated samples were sampled at intervals of fifteen days and were analysed for exchangeable, water, soluble and reducible Mn and for exchangeable and available Fe.

The pH and electrical conductivity were measured in 1 : 5 soil water suspension at 25 ± 1°. Organic matter was estimated as per Walkley and Black's⁷ method.

Water soluble, exchangeable and reducible Mn were estimated colorimetrically according to Jackson⁸ using Leeper's method as modified by Sherman and Harmer⁹ with normal ammonium acetate (pH-7) as extractant and 85% orthophosphoric acid and potassium periodate as colour reagents. A 2% hydroquinone solution of normal ammonium acetate was used as extractant for reducible manganese. The absorbance was recorded using a Bausch and Lomb spectronic '20' reading at 525 nm. Exchangeable and available iron were determined spectrophotometrically by Saywell's¹⁰ method using normal ammonium acetate (pH-7) and ammonium acetate (pH-4.8) as extractant respectively; and hydroxylamine hydrochloride and orthophenanthroline as colour reagents. Absorbance was recorded at 490 nm. Blanks were used in all the cases.

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The data were subjected to statistical analysis of variance according to the two way classification with one observation per cell, the null hypothesis being the equality of the effects of different doses and different time intervals. Correlation coefficients were also calculated.

reducible and active Mn in presence of BHC with different doses at various time intervals of time are represented in Tables 1 to 4. Results for exchangeable and available Fe are recorded in Tables 5 and 6. Each datum in the table is a mean of triplicate values.

Results and Discussion

The data on the water soluble, exchangeable,

The results show that with the application of BHC there was no significant change in pH and electrical conductivity of the soil.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF BHC ON WATER SOLUBLE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Doses in g per kg of soil	Water soluble manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.00	3.26	4.43	5.68	5.00	4.54	3.95	3.35	4.32
0.10	3.23	5.69	7.50	6.82	6.25	5.56	5.00	5.72
0.20	3.22	6.87	8.75	7.89	7.14	6.58	6.00	6.64
0.25	3.26	8.06	10.71	10.00	9.09	7.89	7.30	8.05
0.30	3.20	6.82	8.33	7.50	6.97	6.25	5.70	6.39
0.40	3.23	5.98	7.50	6.67	6.10	5.71	5.10	5.75
0.50	3.22	5.00	6.58	5.98	5.55	4.76	4.20	5.04
Average	3.23	6.12	7.86	7.12	6.52	5.81	5.26	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 61.84, 0.292.
Variance ratio and L.S.D. for dosage = 41.46, 0.292.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF BHC ON EXCHANGEABLE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Doses in g per kg of soil	Exchangeable manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.00	8.90	13.75	16.00	14.38	13.75	13.00	12.50	13.18
0.10	8.85	15.00	19.38	16.50	15.79	15.00	14.00	14.93
0.20	8.94	19.38	21.25	20.00	19.23	18.46	16.70	17.71
0.25	8.90	22.50	25.00	22.00	21.25	20.64	19.80	20.01
0.30	8.96	20.00	22.00	19.38	18.44	17.84	17.00	17.66
0.40	8.98	18.75	20.00	18.00	17.07	16.32	15.60	16.39
0.50	8.92	14.32	17.50	15.00	14.26	13.52	12.90	13.76
Average	8.92	17.68	20.16	17.89	17.11	16.39	15.50	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 54.75, 0.721.
Variance ratio and L.S.D. for dosage = 25.90, 0.721.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF BHC ON REDUCIBLE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Doses in g per kg of soil	Reducible manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.00	61.74	56.82	55.52	57.26	57.91	58.05	58.15	57.92
0.10	61.94	56.19	54.37	57.20	57.40	57.82	58.80	57.69
0.20	61.53	53.68	52.33	53.67	54.59	54.87	56.30	55.28
0.25	61.90	51.08	48.83	50.89	51.69	52.00	52.40	52.68
0.30	61.71	52.42	51.70	53.37	53.82	54.15	54.30	54.50
0.40	61.85	53.21	53.38	55.26	55.87	56.09	56.80	56.07
0.50	61.89	56.91	54.16	56.70	57.27	58.22	58.40	57.65
Average	61.79	54.33	52.90	54.91	55.52	55.89	56.45	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 25.21, 0.836.
Variance ratio and L.S.D. for dosage = 10.50, 0.836.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF BHC ON ACTIVE MANGANESE OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Doses in g per kg of soil	Active manganese in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.00	73.90	75.00	77.20	76.64	76.20	75.00	74.00	75.42
0.10	74.02	76.88	81.25	80.52	79.53	79.38	77.80	78.48
0.20	73.69	79.93	82.33	81.56	80.96	79.93	79.00	79.63
0.25	74.06	81.64	84.54	82.89	82.03	80.52	79.50	80.74
0.30	73.87	79.24	82.03	80.25	79.23	78.24	77.00	78.55
0.40	74.06	77.94	80.88	79.93	79.04	78.12	76.50	78.07
0.50	74.03	76.29	78.24	77.68	77.08	76.50	75.50	76.45
Average	73.95	78.13	80.92	79.92	79.16	78.24	77.04	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 22.24, 0.744.
Variance ratio and L.S.D. for dosage = 10.80, 0.744.

An examination of Table 1 showed that compared to control, water soluble Mn increased significantly. Maximum value reached with 0.25 g of BHC at 30 days and then declined. The increase in water soluble Mn was 10.7 ppm from 3.2 ppm. The influence of the doses was in the order 0.25 > 0.2 > 0.3 > 0.4 > 0.1 > 0.5 > 0.0 g of BHC per kg of soil. Similar results with variable intensity were observed in exchangeable and active Mn (Tables 2 and 4). With the 0.25 g dose of BHC the increase in exchangeable Mn was 25.0 from 8.9 ppm and in active Mn from 74.0 to 84.5 ppm at an interval of 30 days. The influence of the doses for exchangeable Mn was in the order 0.25 > 0.3 > 0.2 > 0.4 > 0.1 > 0.5 > 0.0 g of BHC per kg of soil and 0.25 > 0.2 > 0.3 > 0.1 > 0.4 > 0.5 > 0.0 g for active Mn.

Various workers¹¹ have reported the mechanisms by which an increase in availability of water soluble, available and active Mn occurred in fumigated and unamended soil. The fact that all the three forms of Mn simultaneously increased and then declined showed an effect of both biological and chemical factors on the Mn status of the soil under study. Aligarh soils have been found to contain hard nodular concretions of manganiferous deposits^{1,2}.

The increase in water soluble, available and active Mn occurred, may be due to the solubilising effects caused by soil fungi *Aspergillus niger*¹³ and/or bacteria *Thiobacillus*; the liberation of Mn from organic matter by the stimulated activity of fumigant resistant bacteria which led to decomposition of organic matter as the soil was wetted with water. These results found support, with the work of

Wensley¹⁴ and Martin *et al.*¹⁵, who reported an enhanced microbial activity in soils as a result of fumigation; with the work of Klemmer¹⁶ who noticed that lower doses of certain eradicator type chemicals produced greater, reinvasion potentials in soils; and with the results of Smith¹¹ who found an increase in water soluble and available Mn²⁺ on fumigation. With the toxic effect of higher doses of the chemical on the soil micro-organisms, the stimulated effect declined after a certain period, and the equilibrium shifted towards Mn⁴⁺ resulting in a decrease of Mn²⁺ form (Table 3). The decline in water soluble and exchangeable Mn with passage of time appeared, may be due to the dissipation of the organic chemical with re-establishment of pesticide sensitive Mn oxidising bacteria such as *Bacillus*, *Actinomyces*, *Aerobacter* etc. The results were in agreement with the findings of Charles and Paul¹⁷.

Correlation coefficient data also support the above conclusions. Thus while exchangeable Mn was positively correlated to water soluble form ($r^2=0.973$), there was a negative correlation between exchangeable and reducible Mn ($r^2 = -0.971$).

An examination of Tables 5 and 6 showed that exchangeable and available Fe significantly increased, reached a maximum value with 0.25 g dose of BHC at 30 days of its application and then decreased significantly. The effect of the doses on the increase of exchangeable Fe was 0.25 > 0.2 > 0.3 > 0.4 > 0.1 > 0.5 > 0.0 g BHC per kg soil and 0.25 > 0.3 > 0.2 > 0.1 > 0.4 > 0.5 > 0.0 g for available Fe. The maximum increase for exchangeable Fe was 25.0 ppm from 12.2 ppm (Table 5) and 58.9 ppm from 39.4 ppm for available Fe (Table 6).

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF BHC ON EXCHANGEABLE IRON OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Doses in g per kg of soil	Exchangeable iron in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.00	12.14	14.29	16.42	15.22	14.65	13.57	12.90	14.17
0.10	12.22	17.14	19.28	18.02	17.49	16.37	15.70	16.60
0.20	12.35	19.99	22.50	21.42	20.71	19.29	18.50	19.25
0.25	12.24	21.89	25.00	23.57	22.14	20.72	20.00	20.79
0.30	12.14	19.46	22.14	21.04	19.19	18.92	18.10	18.83
0.40	12.55	18.03	20.71	19.73	18.75	17.35	16.50	17.66
0.50	12.34	16.60	19.11	18.03	17.14	15.73	15.00	16.28
Average	12.28	18.20	20.74	19.58	18.90	17.42	16.57	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 42.50, 0.640.
Variance ratio and L.S.D. for dosage = 26.37, 0.640.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF BHC ON AVAILABLE IRON OF SOIL WITH VARIATION IN CONCENTRATION AND TIME

Doses in g per kg of soil	Available iron in ppm at various days							Average
	1	15	30	45	60	75	90	
0.00	39.40	47.14	50.00	48.58	47.17	46.34	45.50	46.30
0.10	39.34	49.27	52.13	50.00	48.58	47.62	47.80	47.82
0.20	39.78	51.40	54.97	52.84	50.71	49.96	49.00	49.81
0.25	39.42	54.95	58.92	54.66	53.53	53.44	51.60	52.22
0.30	39.57	52.09	55.37	52.23	50.81	49.88	49.00	49.85
0.40	39.34	49.96	52.09	50.67	48.54	47.62	46.80	47.86
0.50	39.42	42.73	49.96	48.54	46.31	45.60	44.80	46.05
Average	39.47	50.36	53.35	51.07	49.38	48.49	47.78	

Variance ratio and L.S.D. for days = 501.25, 0.300.
Variance ratio and L.S.D. for dosage = 124.94, 0.300.

TABLE 7—CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS BETWEEN DIFFERENT FORMS OF MANGANESE AND IRON

Sl. No.	Form	Water soluble Mn	Reducible Mn	Exchangeable Fe	Available Fe
1.	Exchangeable Mn	0.973	-0.971	0.976	0.978
2.	Water soluble Mn	-	-0.930	-0.973	-0.971
3.	Reducible Mn	-	-	-0.932	-0.956
4.	Exchangeable Fe	-	-	-	0.936

An examination of Table 7 showed that there existed significant positive correlation between exchangeable Mn and exchangeable and available Fe ($r^2=0.976$ and 0.978 respectively) as well as between water soluble Mn and exchangeable and available Fe ($r^2 = 0.973$ and 0.971 respectively). There was also a positive correlation between exchangeable and available Fe ($r^2 = 0.936$). The exchangeable and available Fe, however, were negatively and significantly correlated to reducible Mn ($r^2 = -0.932$ and -0.956 respectively).

The above results pointed to the fact that conditions affecting Fe and Mn availability in soils were of similar type, a view in accordance with results of Smith¹¹. It appeared that, reducible character of organic matter in soil and its microbial decomposition with liberation of acids, the drop in oxidation-reduction potential in moist conditions of the soil, stimulation in the activity of micro-organism by pesticides extending upto a period of about 30 days and favourable pH¹⁹ all contributed towards an increase in exchangeable and available Fe. The decline in available and exchangeable Fe with passage of time appeared, may be due to the fact that with dissipation of the organic chemical, the stimulatory effects decline; and Fe bacteria take over both the forms. Same results were also observed by Pringsheim^{19,20} and Alexander³.

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